

DEVELOPMENT OF ACADEMIC MOBILITY OF STUDENTS IN THE CONDITIONS OF DIGITALIZATION

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Abstract. *The introduction of joint education faculties in higher education institutions, the use of digital transformations in order to activate student exchanges will help to improve the system of implementing academic mobility.*

The article highlights the development of online education in higher education institutions, the search for new ways and forms of inter-university cooperation, and the development of academic mobility of students in the context of digitization.

Keywords: *exchange, digital transformation, academic mobility, online learning, mission, competence, strategy, education system.*

Today's era of globalization, as a process of strengthening ties between countries and peoples, shapes human development trajectories in every sphere of social life. Despite the fact that there are different opinions about the positive impact of globalization on the development of national science and culture, globalization can be considered a new stage of international relations. Integrating educational processes into world standards is one of the important components of global globalization today. At the same time, there are also processes of internationalization, understood in a broad sense as "...the orientation of the object to the international dimension of its activity..." [2].

The implementation of international cooperation in the field of higher education, as well as the involvement of foreign students in basic educational programs, is carried out within the framework of the development of academic mobility of students. Scientific and cultural exchange between higher education institutions of different countries is a priority task aimed at creating a highly competitive education system in New Uzbekistan [3], which is confirmed by the state migration and education policy. The main form of international cooperation in the field of higher education is the academic mobility of students, which is defined as the movement of students to foreign educational institutions for the purpose of short-term education within the framework of student exchange programs. In connection with the introduction of joint education faculties in higher education institutions of our country, in order to activate these exchanges, it is required to improve the system of implementing academic mobility based on digital transformation. New strategic tasks were defined for the development of online education in higher education institutions and the search for new ways and forms of inter-university cooperation.

The urgency of developing students' academic mobility in the conditions of digitalization is explained by the need to improve the necessary competencies of students, the development and improvement of the intercultural environment in the educational institution is required, which should be aimed at forming a strategy of personal education and professional development and meeting the social and personal needs of each student.

To date, certain experience has been accumulated on the integration of the Bologna process into the educational system of Uzbekistan, the positive and negative sides of this process have been highlighted, and the main aspects of organizing academic mobility in higher education

institutions have been formed. In the context of the implementation of the Bologna Declaration, the problems of internationalization of higher education were highlighted by V.I.Baydenko [4], O.P.Marinenko [5] and others.

In many foreign studies, the term "international academic mobility" is used for academic mobility. Today, "transnational/cross-border mobility" is also used.

The axiological approach allows to consider academic mobility as a socially and personally significant value, it is an integral form of the existence of intellectual potential and reflects the realization of the internal need for this potential in the field of movement, political relations and connections in the social, economic, cultural space. Academic mobility is the ability to shape one's own educational trajectory, that is, to choose educational institutions, subjects and courses according to one's preferences and aspirations [1].

I.M. Mikova conducted a comparative analysis of the approaches, principles, goals, content, forms, methods and means of academic mobility of students between "Academic mobility of Russian and US university students" [6]. Accordingly, the researcher proposed a unique interpretation of the term "academic mobility", "academic mobility of students is one of the forms of organization of student education, which is a limited period of transfer to another university in one's country or abroad and return to the base university to complete the education". I.M. Mikova emphasizes the following as the main principles of organizing student mobility:

- duration of study at a foreign university - a whole academic year or one semester;
- use of English or the national language of the country during education;
- free education for students on mobile educational programs;
- reimbursement of third-party expenses by the student;
- to be taken into account by the higher education institution to which the results of the evaluated student who has transferred credit at a foreign university are sent;
- the possibility of obtaining joint and two diplomas.

The concept of "academic mobility" has its own interpretation in different countries. Academic mobility mainly refers to various educational programs and student exchange programs. With the development of integration processes in Europe, this concept began to be more widely accepted, elements of programs related to mobility are being created to improve the qualifications of their pedagogical staff and scientific programs. In digitization of these processes, a number of tasks are set before the administration of the educational institution, including:

- formation of information-technological competence of all participants of virtual exchange programs;
- prepare an academic offer for different target groups and send it to all higher education institutions participating in the project (indicating teachers and subjects describing the educational institution);
- preparation of platforms for distance education abroad;
- conclusion of an additional agreement or cooperation agreement between partner higher education institutions;
- promotion of programs in a higher education institution;
- regulation of the student admission process by the local regulatory documents of the higher education institution;
- inclusion of virtual mobility in external quality control;

• facilitate the recognition of training courses and periods in the virtual space based on quality assurance, transparency and mutual trust.

Thus, the changes taking place in the world and the digitalization of the international activities of higher education institutions show the relevance of virtual academic mobility. Distance exchange programs, analyzing the experience of foreign associations and adapting it to the realities of the higher education system is one of the requirements of academic mobility, which allows the implementation of virtual projects.

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